

Examples of Thinking in Horses Learning to Think

Abstract This article presents documented examples of thinking in horses that are learning to think. Unlike ordinary training, where animals acquire conditioned skills, here the focus is on the emergence of cognitive processes: the ability to distinguish, choose, correct, generalize, and maintain intentional actions. The cases include reading words, understanding colors and categories, controlling objects, answering questions, memory-based sequences, and demonstrating preferences. These examples show that with a proper educational approach, horses can act as rational partners, capable of conscious interaction, decision-making, and symbolic communication. Keywords: horse cognition, learning to think, animal intelligence, symbolic communication, decision-making, cognitive behavior, partner interaction, emergent cognition, comparative cognition

Introduction

An ordinary horse acts mainly by instinct and learned reactions. It may be obedient, beautiful, strong, but its world is limited by the habits and signals it has absorbed. A horse that has been taught to think is a different being. It begins to perceive not only commands but also meanings; to distinguish, to choose, to respond. It becomes similar to a child who does not yet know everything, but is already able to think, to understand, and to ask its own questions. This is the transition: from a “reactive animal” to a rational partner who thinks and acts consciously. All these examples can be seen in reality: some of the sessions and experiments are published on my YouTube channel — [elenaquisapiencia](https://youtube.com/@elenaquisapiencia) (<https://youtube.com/@elenaquisapiencia?si=nF4pTiZ3-f4wpqlo>). A detailed description of the methodology and video examples is presented in my book **How to Teach a Horse to Think, Understand and Read**, available here: <https://www.casadellibro.com/ebook-how-to-teach-a-horse-to-think-understand-and-read-ebook/9798231964215/17031087> This is not about tricks or conditioned skills, but about the emergence of cognition itself.

Block 1. Reading: from skill to thinking

Situation 1. Learning words

At first, reading may look like a skill. I give the horse a word, pronounce it aloud, then spell it letter by letter, helping the horse assemble it. With time the horse begins to build the word by sound alone. This still resembles a skill. But once I start asking the horse questions — “What is your name?” — and it spells its own name, or “What is the name of your black friend?” — and it spells the answer, this is no longer a skill. It is already thinking. An additional difficulty is that we work in English: words are not written the way they sound. The horse cannot rely only on sound and must truly think to match letters and words.

Situation 2. Naming body parts

I touch a part of the horse’s body, and it assembles the word: leg, head, eyes, ears, back... I try to cover all parts that I know in English, from the nose to the hooves and tail.

Situation 3. Everyday objects

We move to objects the horse encounters daily: bucket, brush, halter, rug. Then I expand the circle: ground, tree, fence.

Situation 4. Actions and verbs

I introduce actions. If the horse trots, I ask: “What did you just do?” — and it spells trot. I do the same with other movements and exercises, so the horse learns not only nouns but also verbs.

Situation 5. Pictures and real objects

I use pictures: show a picture of a squirrel, show a toy squirrel, then the horse assembles the word squirrel. Later, with a set of cards, the horse answers directly from pictures. When possible, I reinforce with real examples: if we meet a dog or cat, the horse sees them and connects them with the picture and the word.

Situation 6. Colors and qualities

The horses know about ten colors. They also understand spotted (our horse Zhora has spots, and the concept was fixed on him). Assignments vary: I ask “Which ball is red?” or show a card with red, and the horse chooses the correct object. They know qualities such as hard/soft, round, big/small/medium. For example, three balls of different size are placed, and the horse chooses the correct one.

Situation 7. Materials

They distinguish materials: stone, leather, metal, plastic. Tasks may include choosing between objects made of different substances.

Situation 8. Spatial orientation

The horses understand up/down. They also grasp left/right easily, even though I sometimes confuse them myself.

Situation 9. Time and order

I often tell the horse the sequence in advance: “First Spanish walk, then trot, then sideways.” After hearing the sequence once, the horse can perform all elements in order without further prompts. This shows memory and the ability to follow a plan.

Situation 10. Natural phenomena and environment

They know rain, snow, sun, sky, clouds, road, field, car(s). I can ask: “What goes on the road?” — and they answer car.

Situation 11. Yes and no

From the beginning I use yes/no. At first it is my feedback to them: yes when correct, no when mistaken. Gradually they start to answer yes/no themselves. Example: “Do you want a treat?” — the horse answers yes or no.

Situation 12. Categorization

I introduce classes: animal and plant. If I ask: “What is a tiger?” — the horse assembles animal. If I ask: “What is a flower?” — the horse assembles plant.

Situation 13. Grouping

For example: “Select everything green.” The horse collects all matching objects.

Situation 14. Food and daily items

The horses know carrot, apple, bread, water, hay, bucket, brush. They recognize them by description, by taste, and can spell them.

Situation 15. Emotions and preferences

They know love, but also like / don't like. I can ask: “What do you like more?” — and they choose.

Block 2. Other examples of thinking

Example 1. Hooping (hula hoop)

One horse only spins the hoop when I wave my arms, matching my rhythm. Another experiments: raising and lowering the head, changing angle, speed, amplitude — searching for how to spin better.

Example 2. Ball control

Three horses push a large ball towards me, but each developed their own way to turn it. - One nudges only with the nose, usually in one direction, sometimes circling around to adjust. - The second skillfully uses the nose both ways, then rolls it with the forelegs. - The third uses forelegs deliberately: choosing which leg to place on the ball, gently adjusting or pushing strongly depending on the needed trajectory. Earlier he often lifted the wrong leg and sent the ball off; now he evaluates precisely which leg to use.

Example 3. Counting

Horses learn numbers by hearing me count steps. Later I introduce cards with digits and dots. Finally they solve simple sums: $2+3=5$, $6-1=5$.

Example 4. Basket

Two horses collect objects into a basket. They must place items not on the handle but to the side, otherwise they fall. If an item falls out, they pick it up and try again. Sometimes they carry the basket to the items instead. If the basket tips over, they set it upright. In the end they bring the basket to me.

Example 5. Catching and returning objects

Three horses catch objects thrown to them. One also throws the item back to me.

Example 6. Answering questions by nodding

Part 1. Basic description One horse answers questions with head movements: nodding for yes, shaking for no. At first I guided him, but now he responds on his own. Sometimes he begins to answer too early, but after hearing the full question, he corrects himself. This shows real understanding. Part 2. Example questions - "Are you a horse?" — Yes. - "Are you a big horse?" — Yes. - "Are you a small horse?" — No. - "Are you strong?" — Yes. - "Are you fast?" — No. - "Are you the smartest horse in the world?" — Yes. - "Is Zhora smarter than you?" — No. - "Is Zhora a smart horse?" — Yes. - "Are you black?" — Yes. - "Are you a human?" — No. - "Am I a human?" — Yes. - "Are you a cat/dog/tree?" — No. - "Do you like treats?" — Yes. - "Do you like carrots?" — Yes. - "Do you like something inedible?" — sometimes Yes (like the ball, because he enjoys it). - "Do you like playing with the ball?" — Yes. - "Do you like learning?" — Yes. - "Do you like when I pet or scratch you?" — Yes (and he leans in to be stroked). - "Do you like me?" — he often smiles instead of nodding. Part 3. Traps and close words I intentionally create "traps" to test if he listens to meaning. For example, I ask in sequence: "Do you like to read?" and "Do you like to be ridden?" (read/ride). He answers yes to reading, no to riding. Or: "Is Zhora a smart horse?" — he starts nodding yes. I continue: "Is Zhora smarter than you?" — he switches to no. Sometimes the opposite: he begins to shake no, but hearing the end, he corrects to yes. These traps show flexible, non-automatic thinking.

Example 7. Object exchange

One horse catches a scarf, another takes it from him and brings it to me, even if they stand in different positions. Each time he finds a way to take and deliver it.

Example 8. Transitions and collection

Horses change gaits and elements (walk, trot, canter, Spanish walk, passage, sideways) on voice commands: slow, faster. They perform transitions while maintaining collection, sometimes carrying a scarf in the mouth. This requires full-body control and conscious adjustment.

Example 9. Retrieval (apport)

They not only fetch thrown objects but combine it with performing exercises or other tasks.

Example 10. Learning speed

Thinking horses learn new skills much faster. What takes months for an ordinary horse may take just a few sessions. If the task requires no new coordination, 2–3 lessons may be enough. For more complex skills, they still learn much faster than untrained horses.

Conclusion

The examples in this note are not the full range of my horses' abilities and ways of thinking. They are the most vivid and demonstrative episodes, where it is especially clear that the horse does not just reproduce a signal, but understands the task, chooses a strategy, holds an intention, works with symbols, remembers and corrects mistakes. With practice, such manifestations become more frequent, and the solutions — more diverse and refined. For me this is the main result: a horse can be a rational partner — in learning, in play, and in exploration.